

Physics-informed Evolutional Deep Neural Network for Transient Pressure Diffusion in Heterogeneous Media*

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1 Generalization of Reference Solutions

The finite volume method is used in this study to generate the reference solution of the transient Darcy equation. Here, the derivation is illustrated for the two-dimensional case, while one- and three-dimensional cases can be extended in the same manner.

Let $\Omega = (0, 1)^2$. Uniform grid points are introduced in the x- and y-directions as

$$x_i = ih, \quad y_j = jh, \quad h = \frac{1}{n-1}, \quad i, j = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$$

We denote

$$p_{i,j}(t) \approx p(x_i, y_j, t), \quad K_{i,j} = K(x_i, y_j), \quad S_{i,j} = S(x_i, y_j)$$

For homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions, the boundary nodes satisfy

$$p_{i,j} = 0, \quad (i, j) \in \partial\Omega$$

Therefore, the discrete equation for the reference solution are constructed only at the interior nodes. For an interior node (i, j) , the permeabilities on the control-volume faces are computed using the harmonic averages of neighboring nodal values. Specifically,

$$\begin{aligned}
K_{i+\frac{1}{2},j} &= \frac{2K_{i,j}K_{i+1,j}}{K_{i,j} + K_{i+1,j}} \\
K_{i-\frac{1}{2},j} &= \frac{2K_{i,j}K_{i-1,j}}{K_{i,j} + K_{i-1,j}} \\
K_{i,j+\frac{1}{2}} &= \frac{2K_{i,j}K_{i,j+1}}{K_{i,j} + K_{i,j+1}} \\
K_{i,j-\frac{1}{2}} &= \frac{2K_{i,j}K_{i,j-1}}{K_{i,j} + K_{i,j-1}}
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

By forcing conservation over the control volume, the discrete diffusion operator at an interior node is obtained as

$$(L_h p)_{i,j} = \frac{1}{S_{i,j} h^2} \left[K_{i+\frac{1}{2},j} (p_{i+1,j} - p_{i,j}) - K_{i-\frac{1}{2},j} (p_{i,j} - p_{i-1,j}) \right. \\ \left. + K_{i,j+\frac{1}{2}} (p_{i,j+1} - p_{i,j}) - K_{i,j-\frac{1}{2}} (p_{i,j} - p_{i,j-1}) \right] \quad (2)$$

Equivalently,

$$(\mathcal{L}_h p)_{i,j} = \frac{1}{S_{i,j} h^2} \left[K_{i+\frac{1}{2},j} p_{i+1,j} + K_{i-\frac{1}{2},j} p_{i-1,j} + K_{i,j+\frac{1}{2}} p_{i,j+1} \right. \\ \left. + K_{i,j-\frac{1}{2}} p_{i,j-1} - \left(K_{i+\frac{1}{2},j} + K_{i-\frac{1}{2},j} + K_{i,j+\frac{1}{2}} + K_{i,j-\frac{1}{2}} \right) p_{i,j} \right] \quad (3)$$

This discrete form is a two-point flux approximation. The harmonic average of K is used to approximate the effective conductivity between neighboring grid cells, while $S_{i,j}$, as the storage coefficient at the control-volume center, appears in the discrete diffusion operator through the factor $1/S_{i,j}$.

All interior nodal pressures are arranged into a vector in a prescribed order,

$$p(t) = [p_{1,1}(t), p_{1,2}(t), \dots, p_{n-2,n-2}(t)]^T \quad (4)$$

This gives the semi-discrete system

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = L_h p, \quad (5)$$

where L_h is the diffusion matrix obtained from the above finite volume discretization. For interior nodes adjacent to the boundary, if a neighboring node lies on the boundary, the corresponding boundary pressure is given by the homogeneous Dirichlet condition and is incorporated into the matrix system as a known term.

In the time direction, the implicit Euler method is used to generate the reference solution. Let p^m denote the interior nodal pressure at $t_m = m\Delta t$. Then

$$\frac{p^{m+1} - p^m}{\Delta t} = L_h p^{m+1}. \quad (6)$$

Therefore, at each time step, the following linear system is solved:

$$(I - \Delta t L_h) p^{m+1} = p^m. \quad (7)$$

Given the initial pressure field $p_0(x, y)$, the initial interior nodal values are

$$p^0 = [p_0(x_i, y_j)]_{i,j=1}^{n-2}. \quad (8)$$

The above implicit Euler system is then repeatedly solved to obtain the reference solution at all time levels.

Remark 1.1. In Case 3, the permeability $K(\mathbf{x})$ contains discontinuous low-permeability regions, representing low-permeability inclusions or barriers. In this situation, $K(\mathbf{x})$ is discontinuous across the material interface, and the strong-form term $\nabla \cdot (K \nabla p)$ may

not be smooth in the classical sense. The reference discretization, therefore, uses the harmonic-average transmissibility on control-volume faces,

$$K_f = \frac{2K_L K_R}{K_L + K_R}, \quad (9)$$

where K_L and K_R are the permeability fields at the two neighboring nodes or cell centers adjacent to the interface. This treatment is equivalent to using a two-point flux approximation at the discrete level and can naturally capture the blocking effect of the low-permeability region on pressure diffusion. In this paper, this reference solution is mainly used to evaluate the prediction performance of neural methods for pressure diffusion problems with discontinuous coefficients. A rigorous analysis of interface flux errors or local mass-conservation errors is left for future work.

2 PI-EDNN Parameter Settings

Table 1: Information of Case 1 in different dimension settings

Dim	Grid	$S(\mathbf{x})$	$K(\mathbf{x})$	$p_0(\mathbf{x})$	T	Δt
1	101	1	1	$\sin(\pi x)$	0.20	1×10^{-4}
2	65^2	1	1	$\sin(\pi x) \sin(\pi y)$	0.05	2×10^{-4}
3	15^3	1	1	$\sin(\pi x) \sin(\pi y) \sin(\pi z)$	0.08	2×10^{-4}

Table 2: Information of Case 2 in different dimension settings

Dim	Grid	$S(\mathbf{x})$	$K(\mathbf{x})$	$p_0(\mathbf{x})$	T	Δt
1	101	$1 + 0.2x$	$1 + 0.4 \sin(2\pi x)$	$\sin(\pi x) + 0.2 \sin(2\pi x)$	0.12	1×10^{-4}
2	65^2	$1 + 0.2x$	$1 + 0.4 \sin(2\pi x) \sin(2\pi y)$	$\sin(\pi x) \sin(\pi y) + 0.2 \sin(2\pi x) \sin(\pi y)$	0.03	1×10^{-4}
3	15^3	$1 + 0.05(x+y+z)$	$1 + 0.35 \cos(2\pi x) \cos(2\pi y) \cos(2\pi z)$	$\sin(\pi x) \sin(\pi y) \sin(\pi z) + 0.15 \sin(2\pi x) \sin(\pi y) \sin(\pi z)$	0.05	1×10^{-4}

Table 3: Information of Case 3 in different dimension settings

Dim	Grid	$S(\mathbf{x})$	$K(\mathbf{x})$	$p_0(\mathbf{x})$	T	Δt
1	101	1	$0.1, x \in (0.45, 0.55)$ 1, otherwise	$\sin(\pi x)$	0.12	1×10^{-4}
2	65^2	1	$0.2, (x, y) \in (0.4, 0.6)^2$ 1, otherwise	$\sin(\pi x) \sin(\pi y)$	0.03	1×10^{-4}
3	15^3	1	$0.2, (x, y, z) \in (0.4, 0.6)^3$ 1, otherwise	$\sin(\pi x) \sin(\pi y) \sin(\pi z)$	0.05	1×10^{-4}

3 Algorithm of PI-EDNN

Algorithm 1: PI-EDNN time-marching algorithm for pressure prediction

Input: Spatial domain Ω ; initial-value condition $p_0(x)$; storage coefficient $S(x)$; permeability field $K(x)$; boundary operator \mathcal{B} ; final time T ; time step Δt ; collocation points $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^{N_c}$; PINN architecture; regularization coefficient α ; and time integrator.

Output: Predicted pressure field $\hat{p}(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{W})$ at time levels t_n .

1 **Step 0: Initialization;**

2 Initialize the PINN parameters \mathcal{W} and construct the trial function $p(x, \mathcal{W})$;

3 **if hard boundary constraints are used then**

4 └ Embed the boundary condition into the trial function $p(x, \mathcal{W})$;

5 **Step 1: Initial-state training;**

6 Sample initial points $\{x_i^0\}_{i=1}^{N_0} \subset \Omega$;

7 Train the PINN by minimizing

$$L_{\text{init}}(\mathcal{W}) = \frac{1}{N_0} \sum_{i=1}^{N_0} |p(x_i^0, \mathcal{W}) - p_0(x_i^0)|^2.$$

if boundary conditions are not hard-constrained then

8 └ Include the boundary loss in the objective function;

9 Set the trained parameters as \mathcal{W}_0 ;

10 **Step 2: Assemble the PI-EDNN projection system;**

11 **for** $n = 0, 1, \dots, N_t - 1$ **do**

12 Evaluate the current pressure representation $p(x; \mathcal{W}_n)$ at the collocation points;

13 Compute the Darcy operator

$$N_i = \mathcal{L}_{S,K}[p](x_i) = S^{-1}(x_i) \nabla \cdot (K(x_i) \nabla p(x_i; \mathcal{W}^n)), \quad i = 1, \dots, N_c.$$

14 Assemble the Jacobian matrix

$$J_{ij} = \frac{\partial p(x_i)}{\partial \mathcal{W}_j}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N_c, \quad j = 1, \dots, N_{\mathcal{W}}.$$

15 **Step 3: Compute the parameter update direction;**

16 Determine the PI-EDNN update direction $\hat{\gamma}_n$ by solving the regularized least-squares problem

$$\gamma_{\text{opt}}^n = \arg \min_{\gamma} \|J\gamma - N\|_2^2 + \alpha \|\gamma\|_2^2.$$

 Equivalently, solve the normal equation

$$(\mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{J} + \alpha \mathbf{I}) \gamma_{\text{opt}}^n = \mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{N}.$$

17 **Step 4: Advance the network parameters;**

18 Update \mathcal{W}_n to \mathcal{W}_{n+1} using one of the time-marching schemes;

19 **Step 5: Output prediction;**

20 └ Evaluate $p(x; \mathcal{W}_{n+1})$ as the predicted pressure field at t_{n+1} ;

21 **return** Pressure trajectory $\{p(x; \mathcal{W}^n)\}_{n=0}^{N_t}$.

4 Collocation-point Distributions for Case 2

To document the collocation sets used by PI-EDNN, Figure 1 shows representative interior collocation-point distributions for Case 2 in one, two, and three spatial dimensions. The collocation points are randomly selected from the interior reference grid and are used to construct the parameter-space projection for the pressure update. This visualization confirms that the selected points provide broad spatial coverage in each dimension, while the number of collocation points is adjusted according to the dimensionality of the computational domain.

Figure 1: Representative collocation-point distributions for Case 2 across spatial dimensions. Grey points denote the interior reference-grid points, and blue points denote the selected PI-EDNN collocation points. The collocation numbers are $N_c = 50$, 500, and 350 for the 1D, 2D, and 3D examples, respectively.

5 Sensitivity Analysis of the Two-dimensional Case 2 Problem

To further examine the numerical robustness of PI-EDNN, we performed a sensitivity analysis for the two-dimensional Case 2 problem with smoothly varying coefficient fields. Three factors were considered: the time step Δt , the number of collocation points N_c , and the MLP width. The final relative pressure error E_p and runtime were used as the evaluation quantities.

Figure 2: Sensitivity analysis of the two-dimensional Case 2 PI-EDNN model. Top row: final relative pressure error E_p . Bottom row: runtime. The columns show the sensitivity to the time step Δt , the number of collocation points N_c , and the MLP width, respectively. For the time-step study, explicit Euler, Crank–Nicolson, and RK4 are compared. For the collocation-count and width studies, the RK4 PI-EDNN setting is reported.

As shown in Figure 2, the time step has a clear influence on both pressure accuracy and runtime. Smaller time steps generally reduce the final pressure error, but they increase the total number of time-marching updates and therefore lead to longer runtimes. This trend is observed for all three time integrators. RK4 gives the lowest pressure error in this smooth variable-coefficient case, whereas explicit Euler has the lowest computational cost but larger pressure errors.

The sensitivity to the number of collocation points shows a non-monotonic accuracy trend. Increasing N_c from a small value improves the pressure prediction, indicating that sufficient collocation coverage is needed to represent the heterogeneous pressure diffusion dynamics. However, further increasing N_c does not always reduce the error and

substantially increases the runtime. This behavior suggests that the overall accuracy is affected not only by collocation density, but also by the conditioning of the parameter-space least-squares problem and the approximation capacity of the neural representation.

The network-width study shows that increasing the MLP width increases the runtime, while the pressure error does not decrease monotonically. A moderately sized network can already provide accurate pressure prediction for this two-dimensional smooth-coefficient problem. Larger networks introduce more trainable parameters and therefore increase the cost of Jacobian construction and least-squares solution in PI-EDNN. These results indicate that the choice of network size should balance approximation capacity and computational efficiency rather than simply using the widest network.

6 Computational Complexity of PI-EDNN

At each time level, PI-EDNN represents the pressure field by a neural network $p(\mathbf{x}; \theta^n)$ and computes a parameter-space update direction by matching the time derivative implied by the governing equation. Let N_c denote the number of collocation points and P denote the number of trainable network parameters. After spatial collocation, the parameter update can be written in the least-squares form

$$J_\theta \Delta\theta \approx r, \quad (10)$$

where $J_\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{N_c \times P}$ is the Jacobian of the pressure field with respect to the network parameters, $\Delta\theta \in \mathbb{R}^P$ is the parameter-space update direction, and $r \in \mathbb{R}^{N_c}$ denotes the discretized right-hand side induced by the pressure diffusion operator.

The main computational bottleneck comes from constructing J_θ and solving the resulting least-squares problem. The memory required to store the Jacobian scales as

$$\mathcal{O}(N_c P). \quad (11)$$

If the least-squares problem is solved through the normal equation, the matrix $J_\theta^\top J_\theta$ has size $P \times P$. Forming this matrix requires approximately

$$\mathcal{O}(N_c P^2) \quad (12)$$

operations, and a direct dense solve requires approximately

$$\mathcal{O}(P^3) \quad (13)$$

operations. Although the actual runtime depends on the implementation, automatic-differentiation backend, hardware, and linear solver, this analysis shows that the cost of PI-EDNN is dominated by Jacobian construction and least-squares solution rather than by neural-network forward evaluation alone.

The total cost is further multiplied by the number of time steps and by the number of stages required by the selected time integrator. Explicit Euler requires one update per time step. Crank–Nicolson requires an implicit or corrected update, which increases the computational cost. RK4 evaluates multiple intermediate stages and therefore requires more repeated residual and Jacobian evaluations. This explains the observed runtime ordering among the three time integrators.

As the spatial dimension increases, more collocation points are typically required to resolve the pressure field. The approximation task may also require a larger network, which increases P . Because the dominant terms scale with both N_c and P , the runtime grows rapidly from one-dimensional to higher-dimensional problems. This computational structure explains why PI-EDNN can be accurate for pressure prediction but remains more expensive than a simple forward surrogate evaluation.

7 Solution Visualizations for PI-EDNN and PINN

7.1 Solutions of Vanilla PINN

7.1.1 One-dimensional Cases

Figure 3: One-dimensional space-time PINN and reference solutions of case 1 for multiple time steps.

Figure 4: One-dimensional space-time PINN and reference solutions of case 2 for multiple time steps.

Figure 5: One-dimensional space-time PINN and reference solutions of case 3 for multiple time steps.

7.1.2 Two-dimensional Cases

Figure 6: Two-dimensional space-time PINN and reference solutions of case 1 for multiple time steps. Top: PINN solution; Middle: reference solution; Bottom: absolute error.

Figure 7: Two-dimensional space-time PINN and reference solutions of case 2 for multiple time steps. Top: PINN solution; Middle: reference solution; Bottom: absolute error.

Figure 8: Two-dimensional space-time PINN and reference solutions of case 3 for multiple time steps. Top: PINN solution; Middle: reference solution; Bottom: absolute error. The standard PINN shows larger errors for the discontinuous-coefficient problem than for the smooth-coefficient cases.

7.1.3 Three-dimensional Cases

Figure 9: Three-dimensional space-time PINN and reference solutions of case 1 for multiple time steps. (a) PINN and reference solutions of multiple time step with absolute errors. (b) Orthogonal slice of PINN solution at final time. (c) Orthogonal slice of reference solution at final time.

Figure 10: Three-dimensional space-time PINN and reference solutions of case 2 for multiple time steps. (a) PINN and reference solutions of multiple time step with absolute errors. (b) Orthogonal slice of PINN solution at final time. (c) Orthogonal slice of reference solution at final time.

Figure 11: Three-dimensional space-time PINN and reference solutions of case 3 for multiple time steps. (a) PINN and reference solutions of multiple time step with absolute errors. (b) Orthogonal slice of PINN solution at final time. (c) Orthogonal slice of reference solution at final time.

In the experiment of three-dimensional cases, vanilla PINN cannot predict the pattern of pressure diffusion.

7.2 Additional Crank–Nicolson-based PI-EDNN Solutions

The Crank–Nicolson-based PI-EDNN results for the constant-coefficient case are shown in the main manuscript. Here, we provide the corresponding two- and three-dimensional results for the smooth variable-coefficient case and the discontinuous-permeability case.

7.2.1 Two-dimensional Cases

Figure 12: Two-dimensional Crank–Nicolson-based PI-EDNN solution of case 2 with multiple time steps. Top: PI-EDNN solution; Middle: reference solution; Bottom: absolute error.

Figure 13: Two-dimensional Crank–Nicolson-based PI-EDNN solution of case 3 with multiple time steps. Top: PI-EDNN solution; Middle: reference solution; Bottom: absolute error.

7.2.2 Three-dimensional Cases

Figure 14: Three-dimensional Crank–Nicolson-based PI-EDNN solution of case 2 with multiple time steps. (a) PI-EDNN and reference solutions, and absolute error. (b) Orthogonal slice of the PI-EDNN solution at final time. (c) Orthogonal slice of the reference solution at final time.

Figure 15: Three-dimensional Crank–Nicolson-based PI-EDNN solution of case 3 with multiple time steps. (a) PI-EDNN and reference solutions, and absolute error. (b) Orthogonal slice of the PI-EDNN solution at final time. (c) Orthogonal slice of the reference solution at final time.

7.3 Solutions of Explicit Euler-based PI-EDNN

In this section, we illustrate the simulation results of PI-EDNN based on the explicit Euler scheme. The network parameter \mathcal{W} is treated as a function of time t , and its value is updated by

$$\mathcal{W}^{m+1} = \mathcal{W}^m + \gamma_{\text{opt}}^n \Delta t \quad (14)$$

where γ_{opt}^n is the optimal direction of gradient changing.

7.3.1 One-dimensional Cases

Figure 16: One-dimensional reference and PI-EDNN solution of case 1 based on the explicit Euler scheme with multiple time steps.

Figure 17: One-dimensional reference and PI-EDNN solution of case 2 based on the explicit Euler scheme with multiple time steps.

Figure 18: One-dimensional reference and PI-EDNN solution of case 3 based on the explicit Euler scheme with multiple time steps.

These results show that explicit Euler-based PI-EDNN performs well for the constant- and smooth-coefficient cases, while the discontinuous-permeability case remains more challenging.

7.3.2 Two-dimensional Cases

Figure 19: Two-dimensional solutions of case 1 based on the explicit Euler scheme with multiple time steps. Top: PI-EDNN predictions; Middle: reference solutions; Bottom: absolute errors.

Figure 20: Two-dimensional solutions of case 2 based on the explicit Euler scheme with multiple time steps. Top: PI-EDNN predictions; Middle: reference solutions; Bottom: absolute errors.

Figure 21: Two-dimensional solutions of case 3 based on the explicit Euler scheme with multiple time steps. Top: PI-EDNN predictions; Middle: reference solutions; Bottom: absolute errors.

7.3.3 Three-dimensional Cases

Figure 22: Three-dimensional solutions of case 1 based on the explicit Euler scheme with multiple time steps. (a) PI-EDNN and reference solutions, and absolute error. (b) Orthogonal slice of the PI-EDNN solution at final time. (c) Orthogonal slice of the reference solution at final time.

Figure 23: Three-dimensional solutions of case 2 based on the explicit Euler scheme with multiple time steps. (a) PI-EDNN and reference solutions, and absolute error. (b) Orthogonal slice of the PI-EDNN solution at final time. (c) Orthogonal slice of the reference solution at final time.

Figure 24: Three-dimensional solutions of case 3 based on the explicit Euler scheme with multiple time steps. (a) PI-EDNN and reference solutions, and absolute error. (b) Orthogonal slice of the PI-EDNN solution at final time. (c) Orthogonal slice of the reference solution at final time.

7.4 Solutions of Fourth-order Runge–Kutta-based PI-EDNN

In this subsection, we will show the results based on the fourth-order Runge-Kutta scheme. The parameters of neural network will be updated by the following scheme:

$$\begin{aligned}
 k_1 &= \gamma_{\text{opt}}(\mathcal{W}^n), \\
 k_2 &= \gamma_{\text{opt}}\left(\mathcal{W}^n + k_1 \frac{\Delta t}{3}\right), \\
 k_3 &= \gamma_{\text{opt}}\left(\mathcal{W}^n - k_1 \frac{\Delta t}{3} + k_2 \Delta t\right), \\
 k_4 &= \gamma_{\text{opt}}(\mathcal{W}^n + k_1 \Delta t - k_2 \Delta t + k_3 \Delta t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

7.4.1 One-dimensional Cases

Figure 25: One-dimensional reference and PI-EDNN solution of case 1 based on the fourth-order Runge–Kutta scheme with multiple time steps.

Figure 26: One-dimensional reference and PI-EDNN solution of case 2 based on the fourth-order Runge–Kutta scheme with multiple time steps.

Figure 27: One-dimensional reference and PI-EDNN solution of case 3 based on the fourth-order Runge–Kutta scheme with multiple time steps.

7.4.2 Two-dimensional Cases

Figure 28: Two-dimensional solutions of case 1 based on the fourth-order Runge–Kutta scheme with multiple time steps. Top: PI-EDNN solutions; Middle: reference solutions; Bottom: absolute errors.

Figure 29: Two-dimensional solutions of case 2 based on the fourth-order Runge–Kutta scheme with multiple time steps. Top: PI-EDNN solutions; Middle: reference solutions; Bottom: absolute errors.

Figure 30: Two-dimensional solutions of case 3 based on the fourth-order Runge–Kutta scheme with multiple time steps. Top: PI-EDNN solutions; Middle: reference solutions; Bottom: absolute errors.

7.4.3 Three-dimensional Cases

Figure 31: Three-dimensional solutions of case 1 based on the fourth-order Runge–Kutta scheme with multiple time steps. (a) PI-EDNN and reference solutions, and absolute error. (b) Orthogonal slice of the PI-EDNN solution at final time. (c) Orthogonal slice of the reference solution at final time.

Figure 32: Three-dimensional solutions of case 2 based on the fourth-order Runge–Kutta scheme with multiple time steps. (a) PI-EDNN and reference solutions, and absolute error. (b) Orthogonal slice of the PI-EDNN solution at final time. (c) Orthogonal slice of the reference solution at final time.

Figure 33: Three-dimensional solutions of case 3 based on the fourth-order Runge–Kutta scheme with multiple time steps. (a) PI-EDNN and reference solutions, and absolute error. (b) Orthogonal slice of the PI-EDNN solution at final time. (c) Orthogonal slice of the reference solution at final time.